

D5.1

Communication and Dissemination Plan

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D5.1

Communication and Dissemination Plan

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

Month 3, March 2021

WORK PACKAGE

WP5

LEADER

LOBA

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

AUTHORS

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**Programme
H2020**

**Contract Number
101000539**

**Duration
24 Months**

**Start
January 2021**

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Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	15/03/2021	Joao Gaspar	General review

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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present the dissemination and communication plan as well as the associated actions that will be implemented during the Transition2bio project. The strategy is integrated under WP5 – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Impact and Sustainability.

The leader of WP5 (LOBA) will be responsible for the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan and will develop the main tools and materials to be used during the project, in constant support with FVA partner who is responsible for the overall social media management and strategy of the project.

All partners will also be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions implementation and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of the project's results. In general, the expected contribution from partners is to:

- Implement promotional and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploit their contacts and networks;
- Supply news and updates for the web portal and newsletter;
- Interact with the project's posts on various Social Media Channels;
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes;

The present document outlines:

- The objectives of the strategy;
- The main target audiences and respective dissemination and communication objectives;
- Transition2bio brand identity;
- The main dissemination and communication tools and channels to reach the audiences;
- The main activities including an indicative timeline for their implementation;

- A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI);
- Conclusions, outlining the dissemination and communication assets and role of the project
- Annex: Transition2bio brand identity.

1. Objectives of the plan

The main objective of the dissemination and communication plan of the Transition2bio project is to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities and timelines on how/when/where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc) to support the dissemination, with the main goal of gathering the ideal conditions to:

- Raise awareness of the project activities and events;
- Communicate and disseminate the findings and results among Transition2bio target groups;
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and stakeholders (including the identification of events, social media networks, press releases, multiplier organisations, etc.).
- Produce the necessary supporting material to ensure an effective dissemination, including printed material (i.e. brochure, poster, roll-up, goodies...) and digital materials (videos, infographics...).
- Create a link to other existing projects belonging to the European Bioeconomy Network
- Facilitate regular communication, through press releases and newsletters, to inform about the latest news and developments of the project to the media.

2. The strategy

The strategy focuses on establishing and executing a realistic dissemination and communication plan in line with the progress of the project and the utilisation of appropriate tools, channels and actions to communicate with the target audiences in a defined timeline.

To achieve dissemination and communication objectives in a timely and adequate manner, Transition2bio consortium will follow the roadmap below:

- **Planning of Activities (M1 – M4):** Identify the communication and dissemination strategy and plan to ensure the best impact of project's outcomes.
- **Implementation Phase (M5 – M24):** Produce a comprehensive set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from the project results to the identified targeted groups.
- **Monitoring Activities (M5 – M24):** Carefully analyse and assess the impact and success of dissemination activities against pre-established key performance indicators (KPIs).
- **Sustainability (M20 – M24):** Identify and establish mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility of Transition2bio outcomes (Task 5.3 and Task 5.4).

2.1 Target audience and dissemination and communication objectives

Target groups	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
General public interested in sustainable lifestyle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Transition2bio toolkit: DEMAND SIDE • Promote Transition2bio events with main regard to all large-scale awareness and public engagement events • Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers • Promote Transition2bio Library as the key repository of bioeconomy materials, with specific focus on awareness-raising and gamified materials for young people • Expand the Transition2bio mailing list (newsletter) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on Info-educational Games • Receive feedback on Transition2bio large-scale awareness and public engagement events: what worked and what did not work, to improve future editions • Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter • Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: user interface and user experience
Teachers, professors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Transition2bio toolkit: DEMAND SIDE • Promote Transition2bio events addressing young people and encourage teachers' and professors' involvement as catalytic factor to involve schools, universities, kids and young students in Transition2bio events • Promote and recruit them for the Trainings for teachers • Promote school competitions to ensure maximum participation of students • Engage them in co-creation workshops to define future skills and related educational needs in the Bioeconomy • Promote Transition2bio Library as the key repository of bioeconomy materials, with specific focus on awareness-raising and gamified materials for young people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on the communication and education toolkits: DEMAND SIDE • Liaise with them to understand how to organise at best events addressing young people to ensure maximum participation and engagement • Receive feedback on Trainings for teachers and related materials: what worked and what did not work, to improve future editions • Receive feedback on school competitions: co-create the best possible activities to ensure maximum engagement of students, and teachers • Receive feedback on potential future skills needed and educational materials for the Bioeconomy • Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: user interface and user experience

Target groups	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
Kids (<13 years old)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Transition2bio toolkit: DEMAND SIDE Promote Transition2bio events and invite them as participants, with main regard to Hands-on Labs Engage them with social media activities, mainly polls, quiz and educational contents, to increase posts' engagement and overall followers Promote Transition2bio info-educational games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: user interface and user experience Engage them (through schools or teachers) before the organisation of Hands-on Labs to identify most entertaining activities Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter Receive feedback on info-educational games
Young students (>13 years old)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Transition2bio toolkit: DEMAND SIDE Promote Transition2bio events for young people, with main regard to info-educational games Engage them with social media activities, mainly polls, quiz and educational contents, to increase posts' engagement and overall followers Engage them in co-creation workshops to define future skills and related educational needs in the Bioeconomy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: user interface and user experience Engage them (through schools/universities or professors) before the organisation of co-creation workshops to identify the best modalities and topics to be addressed to ensure maximum engagement Encourage interaction via social media to stimulate interest in the bioeconomy matter Receive feedback on info-educational games Receive feedback on potential future skills needed for the Bioeconomy
Public procurers (municipalities and regional development bodies interested in adopting sustainable and/or bio-based solutions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Transition2bio toolkit: DEMAND SIDE Promote Transition2bio events with main regard to Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops Promote Transition2bio Capacity Building activities and engagement in the European Bioeconomy Forum Invite them as participants, or engage them as (municipal) hosts for all Transition2bio events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive feedback on Transition2bio Capacity Building activities and on the meetings held with the European Bioeconomy Forum Receive feedback on potential future skills needed for the Bioeconomy and on co-creation workshops: what worked and what did not work for future editions Receive feedback on Transition2bio lessons learnt and recommendations

Target groups	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote recommendations for the creation of the DEMAND SIDE toolkit • Engage them in co-creation workshops to define future skills and related educational needs in the Bioeconomy • Promote Transition2bio Library as the key repository of bioeconomy materials, with main emphasis on policy briefs, action plans and policy recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: user interface and user experience
Bio-based industries, SMEs and large enterprises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Transition2bio toolkit: SUPPLY SIDE • Engage them in Transition2bio events as key-note speakers • Engage them as Advisory Board members • Engage them in co-creation workshops to define future skills and related educational needs in the Bioeconomy • Promote recommendations for the creation of the SUPPLY SIDE toolkit • Promote recommendations for the implementation of awareness and public engagement activities • Promote Transition2bio Library as the key repository of bioeconomy materials, with specific focus on communication and awareness-raising materials • Expand the Transition2bio mailing list (newsletter) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on the communication and education toolkits: SUPPLY SIDE • Receive periodic feedback and insights on project progress as Advisory Board members • Receive feedback on potential future skills needed for the Bioeconomy • Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: contents and their categorization (including website navigability) • Receive feedback on lessons learnt and recommendations
MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (EUBIONET , citizens' organisations, NGOs and other associations,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote Transition2bio toolkit: MULTIPLIERS AND SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT • Engage them in Transition2bio events promoting the EUBIONET to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enlarge the EUBIONET membership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on the communication and education toolkits: SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT AND MULTIPLIERS • Receive feedback on Training for teachers' materials • Receive feedback on events and activities enlarging and promoting the EUBIONET

Target groups	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
brands, retailers, teachers, EU-funded projects and initiatives, influencers, media, policy makers, regional authorities, initiatives, networks, clusters, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Establish synergies and facilitate wide promotion of Transition2bio activities ● Engage them with social media activities to increase posts' engagement and overall followers ● Promote recommendations for the creation of the MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT toolkit; for facilitating the identification of the Future skills for Bioeconomy and for maximising collaboration among projects and initiatives ● Promote co-creation workshops to identify bioeconomy educational needs ● Promote school competitions and Hands-on Labs, engage them as supporters/ co-organisers/ key note-speakers; promote training for teachers ● Promote Transition2bio Library as the key repository of bioeconomy awareness and educational materials ● Expand the Transition2bio mailing list (newsletter) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Receive feedback on future needs related to educational needs in the bioeconomy ● Receive feedback on lessons learnt and recommendations ● Receive feedback on Transition2bio Library: contents and their categorization (including website navigability)

Table 1 - Transition2bio target groups and objectives

2.2 Brand identity

The visual identity of a project consists of a set of elements that forms its graphic individuality.

For the Transition2bio project, LOBA faced the challenge of creating a new unique identity, that at the same time was reminiscent of the BIOVOICES project identity, since the two projects will have to coexist, for example on social media (making use of the same social media pages).

LOBA developed an initial visual identity for the Transition2bio project at M1, having developed the brand manual (annex to this deliverable), deliverable and presentation's template and stationery.

- Logo

Firstly, LOBA introduced the project to its internal team, and as a result the designer thought out different versions of the project's logo, which can be seen in [annex 9.1](#).

After much consideration, we concluded that the logo in [annex 9.2](#) was the best option, since it showcases the perfect balance between the BIOVOICES identity - through making use of similar colours and reshaping its symbolic leaf (which can be seen in this [video](#)) -, whilst at the same time bringing a new set of earthy colours and other components that set the tone for Transition2bio's unique identity.

- Brand Manual

After the final logo was chosen, LOBA created a brand manual (some pages can be seen in [annex 9.3](#)), which was distributed to all partners with the aim of providing them with guidelines on how to best use the logo, the specific font, colours and dimensions, as well as examples of logo applications on various materials.

- Claim

For the claim of Transition2bio, after analysing different alternatives, we opted for "Towards a more sustainable future" ([annex 9.2](#)), which encompasses both the sustainable component of the project and the idea that there's a journey to be made regarding the process of moving closer to the implementation of the updated 2018 EU Bioeconomy.

3. Tools and channels

The achievement of the Dissemination and Communication Plan objectives will be ensured by the complementarity of its component activities. These will ensure both project dissemination and constant and/or specific feedback from stakeholders.

Feedback collection will be developed on an ongoing basis (through website, interactive boards and platforms such as "Miro" and "Mentimeter" during online events, "Make your voice heard" Wall - tested within the BIOVOICES project- during live events, social media activities, as well as during events) and may concern a specific issue or a particular project stage (through communication activities).

LOBA will manage and ensure the ongoing synergy between the activities to make the most out of the content produced within the project, by communicating the knowledge in different styles (infographics, videos, GIFs, images, etc) for different platforms (website, social networks, etc). Therefore, several tools and channels will be used to support the communication of the right messages to the targeted audiences as presented below.

3.1 Website

The first version of the Transition2bio website was launched in February 2021 (M2) as a landing page at the URL: <https://www.Transition2bio.eu/>. Having a landing page at the very early stage of the project allows the Consortium to fully leverage on BIOVOICES social media channels. All website contents will be reviewed by LOBA regarding SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) best practices for a better indexation and accessibility of the project. Additionally, the project will use Google Analytics as its web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help to optimise the website and the communication and dissemination strategy.

Relevant statistics that will be monitored are the following:

Number of visitors;

Number of unique visitors;

Which links and countries the web traffic comes from;

Number of downloaded documents, newsletters, etc.

The details on the structure and contents of the Transition2bio website will be provided in D5.2.

3.2 Social media

Transition2bio will leverage on the more than 6.500 followers across Twitter (3.055 followers), Facebook (1.559 followers), LinkedIn (922 followers) and Instagram (1.441 followers) BIOVOICES social media channels. FVA, Transition2bio partner leading task 2.3 – Social media awareness and public engagement activities – was also responsible for managing the BIOVOICES social media channels, guaranteeing the consistent and smooth transition of such an important asset from the BIOVOICES project to the Transition2bio one.

Social media profile and cover images were adapted accordingly, as can be seen in the images below.

More details on the Transition2bio social media strategy will be provided in D2.1 at M6.

Figure 1 - Social media profile and cover image

The overall objective of social media usage will be to increase awareness about the project and engage with the target audience. Thanks to the appropriate leverage and involvement of multipliers, influencers and thematic groups, as well as a constant monitoring of the megatrends to identify the correct messages and arguments to be adopted, this activity will increase the impact and effectiveness of the Transition2bio awareness and public engagement activities.

The different types of social networks used will be appropriate to reach specific target groups, and likewise the content disseminated will also depend on these groups. The same applies for paid campaigns launched for the promotion of specific initiatives or results, which will be tailored based on contents and the target audience and agreed in synergy with the Consortium.

Twitter: the BIOVOICES Twitter account powered by Transition2bio will be used with more frequency than other channels to post comments and news about the achievements and progress of the project and to promote project reports and participation in events. Project intervention in discussions will be encouraged through the partners' involvement within their networks or personal pages.

Facebook: the BIOVOICES Facebook page powered by Transition2bio will be used to communicate selected developments and outputs of the project (e.g. key events, activities, and important achievements) and to build a strong group of followers and capitalise on the common and overlapping interests of this audience with project concepts and activities.

LinkedIn: the LinkedIn BIOVOICES page powered by Transition2bio will be used in order to increase the visibility of Transition2bio at a professional level.

Instagram: the Instagram account will be used to share photos from relevant events and activities Transition2bio will organise or participate in. It will also serve as a showcase of bio-based products and initiatives to generally raise awareness of the bioeconomy from a more visual perspective.

YouTube: the YouTube account of Transition2bio will be used as an online video repository for all videos produced by the project.

Partners will use their existing social media pages to boost Transition2bio actions. Partners will select the most suitable channels operated by them to share content from the project website and social media pages such as events, project results, relevant insights from public deliverables, fact sheets/ brochures, etc.

3.3 Stationery, promotional materials & goodies

The stationery and promotional materials aim to support partners in their formal and informal communications, such as in the reporting process (i.e. [deliverables template](#)), presentations in meetings and events (i.e. [PowerPoint template](#) available in two different formats - 4x3 and 19x6), participation in events (i.e. [folder](#), [letterhead paper](#), [business card](#)) and mass-mailing announcements or communications (i.e. [email signature](#)).

The other promotional materials (such as a first brochure, leaflet, roll-up, poster, etc). will be developed at M4 and M5 (closely related to the definition and establishment of the Transition2bio conceptual framework of the awareness, communication and educational toolkits – D1.1).

Goodies will also be produced and distributed at events with the purpose of enhancing brand promotion and brand awareness. Goodies will mainly include the logo, URL and claim of the project.

3.4 Press releases

Press releases relevant for the scope of the project will be sent to specific media outlets. Stakeholders will be informed as well.

In addition, for relationship building with the media, LOBA has an updated private database of over 800.000 contacts of journalists based on Agility PR solutions, which is a valuable asset for press release distribution to ensure a wider media coverage, which can be configured for domain-specific or geo-specific campaigns. Furthermore, LOBA's system allows setting personalised email distribution and obtaining email tracking analytics for follow-up campaigns.

3.5 External events

The participation in third party conferences/events will allow Transition2bio to directly liaise with key stakeholders to provide them with constant updates on project progress.

Transition2bio will organise and participate in several events, conferences and presentations during the project. More specifically, Transition2bio already identified the following events

where the participation of the project may be considered (considering the COVID-19 pandemic constraints towards face-to-face events):

Title	Venue	Type of event
ECOMONDO	Italy	Conference/ Exhibition
EUBCE	(TBD)	Conference/ Exhibition
European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology	(TBD)	Conference/ Exhibition
EFIB	Belgium	Conference/ Networking event
Global Bioeconomy Summit	Germany	Conference/ Exhibition
BBI JU Stakeholder Forum	Belgium	Conference/ Networking event
European Roundtable for Sustainable Consumption and Production	(TBD)	Conference
Forum BuyGreen	Italy	Conference/ Exhibition
Maker Faire – International	Italy	Exhibition
BBI JU INFO DAY	Belgium	Conference/ Networking event
European Sustainable Development Week	Europe	Conference/ Exhibition
EU Green Week	Europe	Conference/ Exhibition
ESOF	Italy	Conference
International Bioeconomy Conference	TBD	Conference
11th International Conference on Environmental Engineering and Management	Switzerland	Conference
International Congress on Biomass	Belgium	Conference
Plant Based Summit	France	Conference

Table 2 - External events

3.6 Newsletters

The consortium foresees the production of at least 3 e-mail newsletters during the project, whose purpose will be to raise awareness of the project and its latest news. These newsletters will be sent proactively to the target audience identified, but it will also be possible for interested parties to subscribe via the Transition2bio website. The contacts collected throughout the 3 years of the BIOVOICES project (more than 500 records) will be used as well to disseminate Transition2bio news, in compliance with EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), since the data holder of both projects is the same (LOBA) and the mass-mailing will be distributed on behalf of the BIOVOICES project.

3.7 Promotional videos

We expect the Transition2bio promotional video to be animated and to firstly introduce the concept of “Bioeconomy knowledge” and secondly present project objectives and services in a nutshell. The envisaged length would be approximately 2 minutes.

The definition of contents, core messages, target audience will be supported by WP1 activities and may evolve as the project progresses.

In order to deliver professional-quality videos, LOBA will follow the steps below in close contact with all Consortium members:

- 1) Conceptualisation: creation and development of the strategy and concept idea;
- 2) Pre-Production: development of the final version of the script, preparation of the technical script, and creation of a storyboard and a mood board;
- 3) Production – turning the script into interactive material using Filming & Digital Cinematography, Production - Video & Audio editing, Production - Graphics / 2D / 3D Animation;
- 4) Post Production – joining all elements created in the different production areas, including VFX Production and “Colour Correction”.
- 5) Marketing & Distribution support - development of different multimedia outputs for content strategy support and the on-site and online promotion campaigns in order to start the distribution.

3.8 Actionable Knowledge

In order to create Actionable knowledge content and material, it is first required to extrapolate core information and messages from the output (e.g., Deliverables, interviews, relevant reports, results from relevant EU funded projects, etc.) and convert them into a graphic concept idea. Keeping a consistent design with the Brand identity (colour palette, logo, icons, etc.).

Messages/ mottos ad-hoc may be created for each of the Actionable Knowledge material created.

The phases we will follow for the production of this kind of material are:

1. Understanding the function/output (is it for the project website? Is it for another website used as a multiplier? Is it for paper distribution? Is it for Social Media? Is it for a newsletter?)
2. Identification of the target groups (is it for experts or the general public?)
3. Identification of the most suitable format (flyer, leaflet, brochure, etc.)
4. Definition of main messages to be conveyed via infographic(s)
5. Definition of the key visual (main elements, photographs, data representation via graphs, colours, feel, etc.)
6. Implementation of all the texts
7. Production of final artwork

All Consortium members will be consulted before delivering the final artwork.

4. Tools and channels per target

The following table showcases how each Transition2bio target audience will be approached by type of tool/channel.

TARGET GROUP	DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS						
	Website	Social Media	Flyers/posters	Actionable Knowledge	Press release	Newsletters	Videos
General public							
Kids							
Young students							
Teachers, professors							
Public procurers							
Industry							
SMEs, large enterprises							
CSOs, NGOs, etc.							
EU-funded projects and initiatives							
Media							

Table 3 - Tools and channels per target

5. Unique selling points

For the overall Strategy of the Transition2bio project, it is of high importance to define the key messages and distinguish features of the project to be transmitted to the core target groups. In other words, it is extremely important to define at this stage the **Unique Selling Points (USP)** of the project, as explained in the table below:

USP	Target group	Need/ Opportunity	Key benefit/ Core Message	Differentiation	Del. / Task
Awareness, communication and education toolkits: DEMAND SIDE	Consumers, general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for clear, user-friendly, understandable and informative materials concerning the bioeconomy • Lack of knowledge of the bioeconomy at large • Scattered bioeconomy awareness-raising/ educational materials on the web 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free informative and educational materials tailored to the DEMAND SIDE needs • Core message: <i>What is the bioeconomy?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contents are collected from at least 100 different sources (EU-funded projects; initiatives and platforms; bioeconomy-library.eu; Knowledge centre for bioeconomy; Consortium's past initiatives/ projects) • Materials aiming at raising awareness and educating about the bioeconomy at large 	D1.2 D1.3 T1.1; T1.2; T1.3
Awareness, communication and education toolkits: SUPPLY SIDE	Industry; SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge of the economic benefits stemming from the bioeconomy • Scattered bioeconomy awareness-raising/ educational materials on the web 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FREE informative/ educational materials tailored to the SUPPLY SIDE needs • Core message: <i>What are the bioeconomy opportunities for you?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contents are collected from at least 100 different sources (EU-funded projects; initiatives and platforms; bioeconomy-library.eu; Knowledge centre for bioeconomy; partners' past initiatives/ projects) • Materials aiming at showcasing economic opportunities in the bioeconomy 	D1.2 D1.3 T1.1; T1.2; T1.3
Awareness, communication and education toolkits: MULTIPLIERS AND SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT	Policy makers; Scientific community Multipliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of personnel/ experience/ time to develop a bioeconomy communication strategy • Lack of knowledge on how to communicate research results • Scattered bioeconomy awareness-raising/ educational materials on the web 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FREE informative/ educational materials tailored to the MULTIPLIERS AND SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT needs • Core message: <i>How to communicate and support the bioeconomy?</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contents are collected from at least 100 different sources (EU-funded projects; initiatives and platforms; bioeconomy-library.eu; Knowledge centre for bioeconomy; Consortium's past initiatives/ projects) • Materials aiming at providing skills, methodologies, knowledge and tools 	D1.2 D1.3 T1.1; T1.2; T1.3
Transition2 bio Library	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of centralized repository of bioeconomy materials (other than 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness, communication and education toolkits available online 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built upon a pre-defined methodology for the collection of materials/ contents (T1.1) and fed with contents (T1.2) 	D1.5 T1.1; T1.2; T1.4

		<p>“bioeconomy-library.eu”)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition2bio partners (FVA and LOBA) have developed and are currently hosting the existing “bioeconomy library” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioeconomy tools, databases, platforms, good practices, contents available online and easily accessible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built upon the existing bioeconomy-library (hosted by FVA partner and co-developed with LOBA) • Community based on the European Bioeconomy Network 	
Transition2bio trainings and training materials	Teachers, professors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioeconomy training materials addressing teachers and professors, stemming from multidisciplinary experience and projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free materials and trainings delivered during ad-hoc events, creating momentum and initial community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials stemming from previous projects, improved and adapted according to face2face workshop results 	T2.2.3; D2.3; D2.4; D2.5

Table 4 - Transition2bio Unique Selling Points

6. Timeline

In this chapter we provide an indicative timeline for all WP5 related activities expected to be implemented throughout the lifespan of Transition2bio project. The chapter is divided into:

- Timeline for the creation of Actionable Knowledge materials
- General timeline of dissemination and communication activities

6.1 Timeline for the creation of Actionable Knowledge materials

The creation of Actionable Knowledge (AK) materials belongs to the so called “content creation phase”, consisting in the identification and conversion of Transition2bio outputs into concise, visually attractive, user-friendly visual material. The table below lists some of the dissemination materials that will transform the project outcomes into Actionable Knowledge for the stakeholders. The entire consortium will collaborate in the creation of the contents, while LOBA will work on the design of the materials. It is important to underline that such a list (and timing) is indicative and more/less materials could be produced in the course of the project lifespan.

Transition2bio activities	Target	Actionable Knowledge (AK)	Months
T1.2 Collection of contents, tools, databases, platforms and good practices	All	AK#1: <i>Bioeconomy materials mapped by Transition2bio (an example is available HERE)</i>	M10 (Initial) M24 (Final)
T1.3 Production of the toolkits	All	Infographic#1 (Summary): <i>Transition2bio toolkits for SUPPLY SIDE; DEMAND SIDE; MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (an example is available HERE)</i>	M23

T2.1 Large scale awareness and public engagement events	General public	AK#2: <i>Insights from Transition2bio large scale events</i>	M12 (Initial) M22 (Final)
T2.2 Awareness and engagement of young people	Kids	AK#3: <i>Insights from the hands-on labs</i>	M21
	Young students	AK#4: <i>Transition2bio games and competitions</i>	M19
	Kids and young students	Infographic#2: <i>Transition2bio school competitions and winners</i>	M20
T3.1 Communication and education mentoring activities	Public procurers, policy makers	Infographic#3: <i>Transition2bio communication and education activities: meetings, trainings and webinars</i>	M9
T3.2 Mutual learning and capacity building activities			
T3.3 Future skills for the Bioeconomy	Young students, teachers, professors	AK#5: <i>Future skills and educational needs in the Bioeconomy</i>	M11 (Initial) M21 (final)
T4.1 Extending the European Bioeconomy Network	Multipliers	AK#6: <i>The European Bioeconomy Network</i>	M7
T4.3 Annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops of the European Bioeconomy Network		AK#7: <i>Insights from the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops of the European Bioeconomy Network</i>	M17
T5.3 Impact, exploitation and sustainability	All	AK#8: <i>Transition2bio Exploitation Plan</i>	M8 (Initial) M23 (Final)
T5.4 Lessons learnt and recommendations	Public procurers, general public, SMEs and industry	AK#9: <i>Lessons learnt and recommendations</i>	M24

Table 5 - Actionable Knowledge materials

6.2 General timeline of dissemination and communication activities

The table below aims at providing a general overview on the timing of each dissemination and communication activity/ material from M1 until M24.

Year 1					
Month	Dissemination activity				
M1	Creation of the Transition2bio visual identity		Mapping Transition2bio target audience (T5.1)		
M2					
M3	Launch of the website and social media				
	Creation of the Transition2bio mailing list (outlets)				
M4	Creation of Social Media pages			Focus on events (T2.1; T2.2; T3.2; T3.3; T4.3)	
	Creation of the Newsletter subscription form				
	Transition2bio Flyer#1				
M5	Transition2bio Rollup#1		Online engagement activities (T2.3; T4.2)		
	Press Release #1				
M6	Transition2bio promotional video				Newsletter contact list enlargement
	Transition2bio Brochure#1				
M7	AK#6				
M8	Newsletter#1	AK#9 (Initial)			
M9	Transition2bio Library – 1st release				
M10	AK#1 (Initial)				
M11	AK#5 (Initial)				
M12	AK#2 (Initial)				
Year 2					
Month	Dissemination activity				
M13	Press release#2		Newsletter contact list enlargement		
M14	Transition2bio brochure#2				
M15	(eventual) Roll-up#2; Flyer#2				
M16	Newsletter#2				
M17	AK#7				
M18	Press release#3				
M19	AK#4				
M20	Infographic#2				
M21	AK#3	AK#5 (Final)			
M22	AK#2 (Final)				
M23	Infographic#1	AK#9 (Final)			
M24	Newsletter#3			Focus on events (T2.1; T2.2; T3.2; T3.3; T4.3)	
	AK#1 (Final)				
	AK #9				
Online engagement activities (T2.3; T4.2)					

Table 6 - Timeline of dissemination and communication activities

7. EXPECTED RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Tools channels &	Metrics method	Expected results
Website	Number of visits, time spent on the website and returning visitors; Number of countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 300 visits per month. - More than 90% of visitors spending 1 minute or more on the website - More than 50% of visits to be from returning visitors from 60 different countries
Flyers/ Posters/ Roll-ups	Number of items distributed vs number of contacts from stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1.600 flyers distributed - 100 contacts showing interest in receiving detailed information
Social media	Number of members and posts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involvement of at least 3.000 followers in the social media with 200.000 unique visitors - Publication of at least 2.000 posts - Establishment of 4 social media profiles in 4 social media channels
Press releases	Clipping/publications coverage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 4 publications
Newsletter	Newsletter dispatched	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 3 newsletters dispatched
Promotional videos	Number of visualizations and shares	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1.000 views and 100 shares
Events/ meetings	Number of participations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 1 participation per partner in external events

Table 7 - Key performance indicators

8. Conclusions

Transition2bio can rely on relevant and consolidated dissemination and communication assets related to the bioeconomy, developed by Consortium partners in the course of the BIOVOICES, Biobridges, Bloom and LIFT/EU/BBi JU-funded projects.

Such assets, ranging from social media channels, mailing lists, platforms (e.g., the [Lift Library](#), the [European Bioeconomy Network](#) or the [Bioart Gallery](#)) to databases and methodologies to bridge innovative bio-based businesses with big brands (e.g., [Bridge2brands](#) format), will serve as a basis for Transition2bio to effectively increase its impact on relevant target groups.

Additionally, they will play a crucial role at the very early stages of the project, on the one hand by guaranteeing a wide audience base (building a considerable audience basis on social media and compiling newsletter mailing lists takes months and efforts at the beginning of an EU-funded project), and on the other by providing since the beginning the project with tangible contents, materials, knowledge and tools to offer to the audience, other than those to be produced by Transition2bio itself (e.g., during WP1 activities).

The use of such assets will be assessed and “activated” in the course of the project lifespan.

Furthermore, when it comes to the corporate dissemination assets of project partners, Transition2bio can already rely on approximately more than 47.000 recipients of mass-mailing, as explained in the table below.

Corporate social media channels of project partners will be used as well to increase the impact of dissemination and communication activities, more details will be provided in D2.1.

Partner	APRE	FVA	ZSI	LOBA	PEDAL	QPLAN	BIOCOM	UNIBO
Recipients	≈15.300	≈1.300	≈1.315	≈21.000	≈1.040	≈1.000	≈5.000	≈1400

Table 8 - Recipients of Transition2bio consortium

When it comes to WP5, Dissemination and communication will play a two-fold role in Transition2bio: on the one hand, it will promote the knowledge gathered and generated in WP1 and the engagement activities to be implemented under WP2, WP3 and WP4; on the other, it will raise the general public’s awareness of the bioeconomy through the curation of social media content on bio-based products and through the Library to be developed under T1.4.

9. Annex: Transition2bio brand identity

9.1 Logo Tests

9.2 Final Logo

9.3 Brand Manual

Safety Margins

The logo requires space around it in order to maximize its visual impact and maintain its integrity.

Safety margins ensure that external elements do not interfere with the recognisability of the brand.

08 Transition2Bio - Safety Margins

Selected Fonts

This project uses just two fonts: Visby CF Extra Bold, Bold, Medium, Regular, Regular and Medium for text, Extra Bold and Bold for titles.

Muli Light, Regular, and Bold, for flowing text.

Visby CF ExtraBold — transition2bio

Visby CF Bold — Towards a more sustainable future

Visby CF Medium — Towards a more sustainable future

Muli Light/Regular — Transition2BIO will build upon the most relevant communication and education EU funded projects and initiatives to contribute to the implementation of the updated 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy and promote the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle by implementing an integrated package of activities addressing a wide range of target stakeholders.

12 Transition2Bio - Selected Fonts

Color Palette

The Transition2Bio identity has pastel colors, based on the bioeconomy and organic materials.

That's the reason why it has a supportive color palette that enhances and complements your communication.

<p>CMYK 0 31 44 0</p> <p>RGB #F9C096</p>	<p>CMYK 0 55 60 0</p> <p>RGB #F18D67</p>	<p>CMYK 12 10 19 0</p> <p>RGB #E7E1D3</p>
<p>CMYK 27 12 18 0</p> <p>RGB #C5D2D2</p>	<p>CMYK 54 15 61 1</p> <p>RGB #87AE7B</p>	<p>CMYK 61 52 66 57</p> <p>RGB #444436</p>

15 Transition2Bio - Color Palette

9.4 Deliverable template

www.transition2bio.eu
info@transition2bio.eu

Number of Deliverable

Deliverable Title here and it may have three or four lines

@transition2bio
f @ in

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Name of deliverable 3 of 12

www.transition2bio.eu
info@transition2bio.eu

Number of Deliverable Title here and it may have three or four lines

DELIVERABLE TYPE	MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY
Report	Month XX, January XXXX

WORK PACKAGE	LEADER
WP Number	Lead Beneficiary

DISSEMINATION LEVEL	AUTHORS
Public	Authors

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
H2020	XXXX	X Months	Month XXXX

Name of deliverable 3 of 12

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NAME THREE HERE	ORGANISATION 3

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
X	DD/MM/YYYY	NAME	MODIFICATIONS
Y	DD/MM/YYYY	NAME	MODIFICATIONS

Name of deliverable 3 of 12

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1. Executive Summary

Here you write the executive summary (up to 1-1.5 page).

Name of deliverable 5 of 12

2. Introduction

Here you put the deliverable introduction.

- 1
- 2
- 3

Name of deliverable 6 of 12

9.5 Presentation template

Write a sentence here

- Clique no icone para adicionar uma tabela

Description of image

8

Thank you

Additional info

Consortium

LOBA

BIOCOM.

UNIVERSIDADE ALameda da Faculdade
de Ciências

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019718

9.6 Folder

9.7 Letterhead paper

9.8 Business card

9.9 Email signature

Consortium

DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE E TECNOLOGIE
AGRO-ALIMENTARI

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